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A rare case series of Primary Spinal Cord Glioblastoma Multiforme. Single institute experience.

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Abstract:

Objective: To describe a single-institution experience with primary spinal cord glioblastoma multiforme.

Background: Primary spinal cord glioblastoma multiforme accounts for only 1.5% of all spinal cord tumors. For these high-grade tumors, overall survival is poor due to their aggressive nature. Unlike the intracranial glioblastomas, there is not a clear consensus on the optimal treatment. Here, we present our institutional experience with two cases of primary spinal cord glioblastoma multiforme.

Design/Methods: Case series

Results: Both of our patients had PSC GBM (WHO IV). The first patient was a male, who had thoracic primary scGBM, he was treated with surgical resection, radiation, and temozolomide; he died 13 months after the initial diagnosis. Another patient was a female who has cervical primary scGBM, she was treated with surgical biopsy and radical radiation with temozolomide.

Conclusions:

We presented our experience and approach towards management of spinal cord glioma. Until now, there is a lack of consensus on the specific management of spinal glioblastomas, there is no standardized postoperative therapy yet. We should report such cases in order to learn from various experiences. (48 hour urine collection) requires stone free periods that some patients, such as this one, may not be able to maintain and ultimately delay diagnosis and require more surgical procedures and medical risks.

Introduction:

Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is a rare malignancy, although this is the most frequently occurring primary central nervous system (CNS) tumor, it is mostly localized to supratentorial space. GBM occurring in the spinal cord is extremely rare, it accounts for only 1% to 3% of all primary spinal tumors. There are fewer than 200 cases of spinal cord GBM that have been reported until now.

Primary spinal cord GBM is rare compared to GBM in the brain probably due to fewer neuroglial cells in the spinal cord. It is seen in younger individuals with a median age of 22 years. It affects both sexes, with more propensity towards males while females usually have a worse prognosis comparatively.

There is no standard of care for spinal cord GBM. The most popular treatment followed is the mirrored management of brain GBM according to Stupp's regimen, which includes maximum safe resection followed by adjuvant radiotherapy and chemotherapy.

Spinal cord GBM is so deadly and so rare that it is unlikely there will ever be a clinical trial. Even though various treatment modalities have been tried, the median overall survival (OS) is just 12 months.

We attempt to present with a literature review, our thoroughly documented cases their clinical presentation, characteristics, workup, and management, done at our institute so that it might be vital for future references and investigations.

Materials and Methods:

We retrospectively analyzed the medical records of the two patients treated at the Department of Radiation Oncology, M. S. Ramaiah Hospital, India between March 2022 to August 2024 for primary spinal cord glioblastoma multiforme.

Case Presentation:

Case 1:

A 29 year aged male, presented with complaints of backache & difficulty walking for 3 months, associated with paraesthesia & numbness of both lower limbs, the right more than the left. He also gave a history of difficulty passing stools & urinary hesitancy with a weak stream. On neurological examination, cranial nerves were intact. His motor examination of lower extremities had a power of 3/5. Sensory examination was significant for decreased sensation below the T6 dermatome. All deep tendon reflexes were 2+ bilaterally. There were no neurological abnormalities of the upper extremities.

He was investigated with an MRI brain which was normal, MRI spine showed an enhancing intradural intramedullary ovoid lesion of 8x8x14mm on T1c at the level of D8 causing increased cord diameter with extensive surrounding edema from level D6 to D11 vertebral levels as shown in figure 1 and 2.

He underwent subtotal tumor excision with D6 to D8 laminectomy. Post-op histopathological examination revealed fragments of moderately cellular glial neoplasm, a tumor composed of spindled astrocytes, displaying moderate nuclear atypia dispersed over a fibrillary stroma, diffuse midline glioma, WHO grade IV. Immunohistochemistry was positive for H3pK27M & OLIG2, and negative for IDH1 pR132H & p53. With ATRX-retained nuclear expression, MIB1 labeling of 12%.

He had a power of 0/5 in both lower limbs post-surgery. He was planned for adjuvant chemoradiation after 4 weeks of surgery, radiation to a dose of 54 Gy in 30 fractions, along with Temozolomide (75mg/m²) 1 hour before radiation. He completed adjuvant chemoradiation. He was on adjuvant temozolomide (150mg/m²) for 1 year. His 1-year follow-up MRI showed stable disease. He died 13 months after diagnosis, due to suspected pulmonary thromboembolism.

Figure 1: The red marked area on the T1c MRI image shows an enhancing intradural intramedullary ovoid lesion at the level of D8.

Figure 2: The red marked area on T2 weighted MRI the lesion causing increased cord diameter with extensive surrounding edema from level D6 to D11 vertebral levels.

Case 2:

A 38 year female, who has hypertension, and type 2 diabetes mellitus, nulliparous, presented with complaints of neck pain and weakness of left side upper and lower extremities for 1 month. No history of difficulty passing stools or urine. On neurological examination, cranial nerves were intact. Her motor examination of the left upper and lower extremities had a power of 2/5. The right upper and lower extremities had the power of 4/5. Sensory examination was normal.

She was investigated with an MRI brain which was normal, the MRI spine showed an enlarged cervical and upper thoracic spinal cord up to the D3 vertebral level, which shows a diffuse altered signal as shown in figures 4 and 5. Heterogenous post-contrast enhancement was seen at C3 to C4 vertebral levels.

She underwent a C3-C6 laminectomy with tumor decompression and biopsy. Post-op histopathological examination revealed fragments of cellular glial neoplasm composed of cells showing astrocytic phenotype and exhibiting moderate atypia dispersed in a glial fibrillary background. Many gemistocytes were observed. Diffuse midline glioma, WHO grade IV. Immunohistochemistry was done, which was positive for H3pK27M, GFAP, and OLIG2. H3pK27Me3 loss of expression, MIB1 labeling of 18-20% in hotspots.

Post-surgery, her motor examination of her left upper and lower extremities had a power of 2/5. The right upper and lower extremities had the power of 4/5. Sensory examination was normal. She was planned for adjuvant chemoradiation after 2 weeks of surgery, radiation to a dose of 54 Gy in 30 fractions, along with Temozolomide (75mg/m²) 1 hour before radiation. She is currently on adjuvant chemoradiation.

Figures 5 and 6: Enlarged cervical spinal cord up to the D3 vertebral level, which shows a diffuse altered signal.

Discussion:

In a literature review Timmons et al reported 153 cases of spinal cord GBM. The median overall survival was 12 months. The median age presentation of spinal cord GBM was 22 years, and there was male predilection. But, a significant predictor of worsened outcome in females compared to males. The most common location is the cervical region, followed by the thoracic region. Compared to other regions of scGBM, patients with gliomas in the thoracic region lived 40 months or longer.

There is no particular consensus for the management of scGBM, however the preferred management is similar to that of the management of intracranial GBM. Therefore, most of the patients undergo neurosurgical operation, either just biopsy or partial resection. A case reported by Marchan et al reported a survival of 64 months where surgical corpectomy was performed in a paraplegic patient.

Although the use of adjuvant chemoradiation is the standard in intracranial GBM, the use of chemotherapy and radiation is still controversial because of their unknown benefit. Radiation to a lower dose of 54 Gy in 28 fractions is preferred compared to brain radiation (60 Gy). This is mainly due to the spinal cord sensitivity to higher radiation doses, which can lead to permanent neurological injury or radiation induced myelitis. Spinal cord gliomas are also considered not radiosensitive tumors, so the lower dose might not be sufficient thereby leading to rapid progression. A case reported by Shirato et al survived an additional 4.8 years after receiving 65 Gy of radiation in 26 fractions. Shirato et al pointed out the higher doses of radiation should only be tried in patients with already compromised motor function and location should preferably be in thoracic or lumbar region, as it may lead to “radio-corpectomy”.

Alkylating agents such as Temozolomide is most commonly used concurrently with radiation as it is a radiosensitizer, usually given 1 hour prior to radiation. Temozolomide is given concurrently at 75mg/m² and adjuvant temozolomide at 150mg/m². In addition to Temozolomide, Bevacizumab is added for its ability to decrease peritumoral edema and mass effect. Other Alkylating agents like carmustine, lomustine, cyclophosphamide and dacarbazine were also used. Non-alkylating agents like paclitaxel and Bevacizumab were also used. There is no significant difference between patients who received Temozolomide versus those who received some other form of chemotherapy. Duran et al found no significant association with temozolomide and prolonged survival.

In Spite of extensive search, we didn't find any information on deterioration due to radiation. Therefore, we should not be so constrained about spinal cord tolerance like done in treatment at other sites.

Conclusion:

Spinal cord GBM is an aggressive disease, and radiation forms an important modality in its management. There is usually a short follow-up of 1

year, with surgery and chemoradiation. Radiation dose of minimum of 54 Gy up to 65 Gy can be delivered considering the already compromised motor function. We presented our experience and approach towards management of spinal cord glioma. Until now, there is a lack of consensus on specific management of spinal glioblastomas, there is no standardized postoperative therapy yet. We should report such cases and their management in order to learn from various experiences.

References:

1. Timmons JJ, Zhang K, Fong J, Lok E, Swanson KD, Gautam S, Wong ET. Literature review of spinal cord glioblastoma. *American journal of clinical oncology*. 2018 Dec 1;41(12):1281-7.
2. Peralta EE, Sánchez LH. Primary spinal cord glioblastoma. *Cureus*. 2021 Oct;13(10).
3. Jokovic M, Somma T, Ilic R, Guizzardi G, Stanimirovic A, Raicevic S, Milicevic M, Grujicic D, Solari D. Primary spinal glioblastoma multiforme. Single center experience and literature review. *Interdisciplinary Neurosurgery*. 2021 Jun 1;24:101109.
4. Shen CX, Wu JF, Zhao W, Cai ZW, Cai RZ, Chen CM. Primary spinal glioblastoma multiforme: a case report and review of the literature. *Medicine*. 2017 Apr 1;96(16):e6634.
5. Shrestha P, Eineichner T, Wilson B, Lam NS. Intradural intramedullary spinal cord glioblastoma: a case report. *Cureus*. 2023 Aug;15(8).

